

Integrated BIM tools for Digital Building Permit

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Abstract

The building permit is the conceded authorization of the public entities to implement the construction phase of a project. It is intended to guarantee a controlled and sustainable development of living environments and built structures that are compliant with all the public regulations.

The traditional building permit procedure is a long and dreadful process that often leads to errors in the design and construction phases and impacts the efficiency of the overall building project. Replacing this analogue, manual and document-based process with a digital, agile and fully transparent method has been a growing interest of the municipalities and the Architecture, engineering, Construction and Operation (AECO) industry simultaneously.

On the other side, the use of BIM is becoming an essential part of the design process. BIM is helping the designers and builders to improve the quality of their projects and save time by significantly reducing errors during the information exchange process. BIM model checking is an essential ally to the automation of Digital Building Permit, enabling to simplify and speed this process.

The goal of the present work is to have an overview on the digitalization of Building Permit together with the methods used for the BIM-based automation of the process. Through the analysis of building regulation focused on fire safety, the research aims to establish rules

to use on the BIM model checking. The rules are the starting point for the two methods of application, using a recognized model checker platform and creating an independent method using visual programming language. The final results of the applications were tested in models, in an attempt to create a vision to develop useful tools for supporting municipalities in setting up their own strategy when adopting the DBP process.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/NbDiVunfDmE>

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